

TOWARD THE PRODUCTION PHASE OF NOAA'S
NEXT GENERATION WATER LEVEL MEASUREMENT SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

The National Ocean Service (NOS), within the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA), operates and maintains a National Water Level Observation Network (NWLON) to accomplish its statutory responsibility for measuring, collecting, analyzing, and disseminating water level data. Because the equipment used to support the NWLON is aging and largely obsolete, NOS is replacing it with a modernized system--the Next Generation Water Level Measurement System (NGWLMS). The NGWLMS is a fully integrated system including new technology field sensors and storage/recording equipment, multiple state-of-the-art data transmission options, and integrated central data processing, analysis, and dissemination subsystems. This paper will report on the results of an evaluation of 20 prototype field units and describe the progress to date on acquiring the overall system hardware and software. The production field units will be characterized and compared to the detailed specifications under which they were purchased. Final system requirements and capabilities will also be outlined.

BACKGROUND

In Fiscal Year 1984, the National Ocean Service (NOS) of the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) began funding a program to update and modernize the field equipment and central headquarters' processing system used to collect, process, analyze, and disseminate water level and other ancillary oceanographic and meteorological data from its National Water Level Observation Network (NWLON). Management of the program was formally assigned to the Ocean Systems Division (OSD), an engineering group within NOS's Office of Oceanography and Marine Assessment (OMA). OSD's engineers work closely with the personnel of the Sea and Lake Levels Branch (SLLB) of OMA's Physical Oceanography Division (POD) where the management and operations for the present NWLON lie and where the program requirements are generated.

The NWLON includes 225 permanent stations with approximately 150 temporary supplemental stations located on the tidal waters of the United States, its territories, and the Great Lakes. Water level measurements are collected and recorded at each station and then processed by central facilities at NOS Headquarters at Rockville, Maryland. The NWLON

is supported by Federal employees at the Atlantic Operations Group (AOG) in Norfolk, Virginia, and the Pacific Operations Group (POG) in Seattle, Washington, who are responsible for station maintenance and periodic leveling of a network of benchmarks. In some areas of the United States, private contractors perform the maintenance and leveling. Data from the NWLON are processed, analyzed, disseminated, and stored at NOS Headquarters.

The primary limitations and operating problems with the NWLON result from the technology used. Each permanent NWLON station is generally composed of an instrument shelter; water level gage, including a back-up gage; stilling well; reference staff or gage; and bench marks. Figure 1 is a simplified graphic representation of a station installation.

Figure 1

Analog-to-Digital Recorder (ADR) tide gages have been used as the principal measurement equipment since 1965. An ADR gage measures water level by means of a float and wire attached to a spring loaded drive. As the water rises and falls, the drum rotates and turns a mechanical shaft encoder that converts the analog signal to a digital reading. Under the control of a timer, the encoded records the water level into a punched paper tape. To filter most wave effects from the reading, the float and wire are mounted in a vertical pipe with

a small orifice at the bottom, referred to as a "stilling well." Water level heights are recorded with a resolution of 0.01 foot.

The gages actually measure the vertical change in height of the water surface relative to the adjacent land. Five times per week tide observers compare the gage readings with either readings from a manually operated electric tape gage (ETG) or visual water readings on the reference staff. The observer writes the staff reading onto log forms and marks the correct time directly on the tide roll. The ETG or tide staff, in turn, is connected by precise leveling to a suite of permanently secured bench marks located in the vicinity of the station. Typically, the leveling is conducted twice each year.

An analog recording pressure gage, viz., a "bubbler" gage, is used to provide backup data at each permanent site and is the primary water level sensor at many temporary and some permanent stations that cannot support a float and well installation. On the average, 75 temporary analog stations are operated each year. The bubbler gages measure the changes in water pressure above an orifice in order to sense the rise and fall of the water level. Nitrogen is bubbled through an underwater tube in order to continually purge water from the orifice. This causes pressure in the orifice/tubing to be proportional to the height of the water above the orifice. A bellows senses the pressure changes and moves a pen on a moving sheet of paper. Accuracy varies depending on tidal range and other environmental conditions and is in the range of +/- 0.1 to +/- 0.5 foot.

The maintenance program required to support these types of equipment is costly and labor-intensive and introduces additional human errors into the data collections process. Furthermore, the equipment is rapidly approaching the end of its useful life and some of the present hardware is no longer manufactured.

Two methods of data retrieval and transmission are used with the present NWLON: (1) mailing of paper recordings and (2) telephone telemetry. At 170 permanent stations, data retrieval is the responsibility of the tide observer. The punched paper tapes and/or analog recordings, comparative staff readings, leveling records, and station documentation are mailed at the end of each month by the tide observer to NOS Headquarters.

Data recording and transmission capabilities are antiquated and inadequate. The practice of monthly mailings by tide observers delays processing and analysis by six weeks. This delay has not been a problem for the present nautical charting system, but will be a problem once efforts are completed to install new generation, on-board computer systems on the NOAA hydrographic fleet. The new system will apply tidal correctors for chart datums in real-time while the ships are at the survey sites.

At present, the data processing functions are fragmented. Budgetary limitations and the various operating characteristics of automated data pro-

cessing (ADP) equipment procured at different times have precluded development of an integrated data processing and analysis system and have resulted in NOS having to operate and maintain nine varied and disparate software systems to gather these data, edit and process the data, produce reports, and maintain a local archive. In addition, these nine software systems run on six different hardware systems and are labor-intensive with respect to quality control and assurance.

PROTOTYPE FIELD UNITS

Because the technology and equipment used to support the NWLON are aging and largely obsolete, NOS is replacing the equipment in the field and at NOS headquarters with a modernized system—the Next Generation Water Level Measurement System (NGWLMS). This modernization program involves a major upgrade of the existing system through complete end-to-end hardware replacement, and the application of technology advances of the last decade. It will include new and additional sensors, improved measurement techniques, microprocessor-based recording equipment, multiple data transmission options, and integrated data processing, analysis and dissemination subsystems (see Figure 2).

Figure 2

The NGWLMS consists of five functional subsystems:

1. Sensor/measurement
2. Data collection and recording
3. Data transmission
4. Data processing and analysis
5. Data and information dissemination

The NGWLMS system design is based on proven, state-of-the-art components involving an integration effort rather than a development effort. A modular approach has been specified to design and incorporate hardware and software to ensure that any repairs or future integration can be made easily.

The NGWLMS concept consists of a core system and an expanded system. The core system addresses the replacement of all five major subsystems as they relate to the NWLON; all of the existing products and services (with major improvements); and specific high-priority new capabilities for products and services, mostly related to near real-time or real-time operations.

The expanded system will provide the capability to satisfy a number of known requirements, or expected requirements, that are not included at the present time because of a need for research and development, major coordination and phasing factors related to other program areas, present funding priorities, etc. These include such things as a special hydrographic module with a radio transmitter, a tsunami warning module, operational links to geodetic Very-Long Baseline Interferometry (VLBI) and Global Positioning Systems (GPS); and full network link to all NOAA oceanic and meteorological services. However, the core system will allow for flexible interface capability and system growth to facilitate later accommodations of the expanded system.

A remote water level sensor is a key component in NGWLMS. As such, thorough test and evaluation of this device was essential to ensure that it meets the performance requirements posed for NGWLMS. Based on previous studies, an air acoustic ranging water level sensor was selected as the basic measurement instrument that will be used in NGWLMS. In May 1984, NOS contracted for the delivery of 36 Aquatrak sensors (Aquatrak is a product of Bartex, Inc., Annapolis, MD). In July 1984, the planning for a comprehensive test and evaluation of these devices by an independent organization, the Applied Physics Laboratory of The Johns Hopkins University, commenced. The objective of this procurement and evaluation was to verify the performance of this sensor and to identify potential problems.

The term front-end subsystem was used to characterize that portion of the NGWLMS that is physically located at a tide and water level station and is referred to as the field unit. It consists of a collection of individual sensing/measurement subsystems (e.g., for water level, air pressure, temperature, wind, current); the data collection and recording subsystem; and that part of the data transmission subsystem that is located at the field stations.

The field unit is a critical element within NGWLMS, and although field units having similar subsystems have been deployed by other agencies, a full front-end subsystem of the precise characteristics required by NOS has not been demonstrated under operational conditions. In September 1984, NOS awarded a contract to The Sutron Corporation for the fabrication of 20 prototype front-end subsystems, incorporating Aquatraks as Government Furnished Equipment (GFE). Table I is a brief hardware description of the prototype field units. Three of these units underwent comprehensive field testing at the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers' test facility in Duck, North Carolina. Following factory acceptance, all the units were installed and evaluated within

the prototype network. See Table II for a list of the locations of the 20 prototype field units.

The laboratory and field test and evaluation of the prototype front-end subsystem or field units was considered critical to continuing any further NGWLMS procurement process. The evaluation was intended to combine all of the elements that represented significant technical and economic risk and to test the basic principles and designs upon which the NGWLMS was based. The field evaluation of the prototype network provided engineering data to verify the performance of the initial design concept. The prototype network served to define the final technical requirements that were included in the Statement of Work and Specifications for subsequent procurement of the production NGWLMS field units.

The data from the prototype field units were transmitted via the Geostationary Operational Environmental Satellite (GOES) system to NOAA's Command and Data Acquisition (CDA) ground station, located at Wallops, Virginia. The data were then relayed from the CDA to the GOES Data Collection System (DCS) control center at the World Weather Building (WWB), located in Camp Springs, Maryland. The NGWLMS program office obtained the data via telephone from the GOES DCS using an IBM-AT microcomputer located at the NOS facility in Rockville, Maryland. This microcomputer was also capable of communicating with each front-end subsystem via dial-in telephone.

A site selection methodology was developed and numerous selection criteria (see Table II) were established to identify both the sites for the prototype network installations and the configurations for the sensing/measurement subsystems associated with these installations. These site selection techniques will also be the basis for establishing the deployment schedule for the production NGWLMS field units.

The prototype units were installed at the selected existing tide and water level stations in such a manner as to provide data correlation with measurements obtained from the existing ADR equipment. The following parameters were addressed with respect to tests on the Aquatrak water level sensor: effects of environmental temperature extremes, temperature gradient errors, fouling effects, and overall measurement quality (i.e., Aquatrak versus ADR). A field history on failures was also logged to obtain an empirical view of reliability.

The other components of the field units - those electronics used for acquiring, preprocessing, and transmitting the data - were evaluated for system capacities (i.e., battery capacity, memory capacity, and auxiliary sensor load), normal system performance (acquisition, preprocessing, and telemetry capabilities), special functions (self-test, parameter downloading, and data recovery capabilities), and reliability.

By September 30, 1986, nineteen NGWLMS prototype units had been installed in the field with one retained at Rockville, Maryland, for test, debug,

and display purposes. Data from these units were analyzed and compared to standard float-punched paper tape field results. The percentage of satellite data returned was over 99.5 percent for 7 sites analyzed when the redundant water level data was used. Statistics from 5 intercomparison sites indicated that standard deviations of differences were less than 0.03 foot between the NGWLMS field unit acoustic gage and the float-ADR gage.

The performance of the Aquatrak was independently evaluated by The Johns Hopkins University's Applied Physics Laboratory (APL) at both their Columbia, Maryland, facility and their Shady Side, Maryland, test facility. Results of the inspection and acceptance tests at Columbia include the following:

- o 2 of 36 sensors failed accuracy/resolution tests; in these cases, the initial calibration was faulty, and easily corrected.

- o None of the sensors failed dynamic response tests.

- o No significant measurement errors were caused by static temperature extremes over the range of -20 to 45 degrees C. Some units ceased operation at the extremes, but resumed when temperatures were slightly moderated.

The objective of the work at Shady Side, Maryland, was to acquire data on errors induced by temperature gradients along the sound tube, and also to begin accumulating qualitative data on performance of the sensors under field conditions. To support the primary objective, the installations were designed to produce temperature gradients exceeding those expected under normal operational field installations. Results included the following:

- o Temperature gradient-induced measurement errors are typically less than 0.1 foot.

- o The magnitude of the temperature gradient-induced errors can be reduced by modifying installation procedures.

- o Application of relatively simple correction algorithms can reduce this error by an order of magnitude or more.

- o Two sound tube temperature sensors mounted on the outside of the sound tube will provide adequate data for temperature correction.

- o Comparisons to a mechanical gage at the site have shown medium-term Aquatrak drift (about 3 months) to be within +/- 0.02 foot.

In addition to the above temperature studies, two test wells at Duck, North Carolina, were instrumented with additional temperature sensors to acquire test data from a more dynamic environment.

By May 31, 1987, the 20 NGWLMS prototype field units had operated for over 175,000 hours, the equivalent of almost 20 years of operation. This indicated a Mean-Time-Between-Failures (MTBF) of approximately 15,000 hours, since the units have experienced only

ten system failures. A system failure is defined as a problem that results in the loss of more than three hours of water level data.

In addition to the total failures, there had been ten partial failures, defined as failures in either the GOES transmitter or telephone modem, requiring field repair. However, because there were two modes of data telemetry, the data were still collected and received at headquarters; and the repairs were made at a convenient time. With regard to the acoustic water level sensor reliability, there were only five failures in 220,000 hours that included prototype network operation and the APL/Shady Side field test.

Because the Aquatrak requires a sounding tube, the effects of fouling were also examined. Based on test results from Duck, North Carolina, and other locations, thick-walled copper tubing used for the portion of the sounding tube that is under water provides fouling resistance adequate enough to require only annual maintenance at most sites and semi-annual maintenance in locations of severe fouling. The present mounting configuration of the sensor allows the cleaning of the Aquatrak sounding tube without requiring divers and releveling of the sensor.

As a result of the tests and evaluations conducted through May 1987, the following conclusions were drawn:

- o the Aquatrak sensor performed satisfactorily,
- o the Field Unit performed reliably,
- o a high percentage of data was received (99.5 percent), and

- o the comparison of the NGWLMS field unit data to the ADR data was favorable (standard deviation of the differences less than .03) with no indication of long-term drift.

BEGINNING THE PRODUCTION PHASE

The test and evaluation of the prototype units provided knowledge and experiences that ultimately led to the following major changes in the specification for the production field units:

- o the successful contractor would provide both the Data Collection Platform (DCP) and air-acoustic sensor

- o the field units would have significantly increased data storage capability

- o the field unit components would be modularly packaged

- o the Backup Water Level Sensor would be part of the field unit

- o there would be a flexible interface for external applications

- o an ancillary meteorological package and an

external modem would be options

- o the telephone baud rate would be increased (300 to 1200 baud)

On November 7, 1986, NOAA's Procurement Office issued a Request for Proposals (RFP) to develop and deliver 250 production field units over a four-year period. Table III is a brief hardware description of what is expected to be built from the specifications in the RFP. Eighty-six companies requested copies of the RFP and twenty-five were represented at the Pre-Bidders' Conference held on November 26, 1986. Several proposals were received on January 26, 1987. After a detailed review by the Source Evaluation Board and its subcomponent, the Technical Review Committee, the successful contractor was selected in July 1987.

With the selection of a contractor for the production field units, NOAA moved from the Concept Evaluation and System Definition and Specification phases of its NGWLMS program and began the Production phase. Deployment of production field units will begin in 1988.

While waiting for delivery of the first field units, the NGWLMS Program Management Office is working with the SLLB to select deployment sites, on a priority basis, for the first 50 units and to prepare an Integrated Logistics Support Plan (ILSP). The ILSP will identify organizational responsibilities for equipment and software maintenance including skill and staffing requirements, facility and equipment requirements, and supporting documentation. It will contain maintenance task descriptions and document maintenance procedures plus plans and procedures for warehousing, accountability and spare parts inventories and for configuration management.

As stated previously, the existing DPA sub-system for the NOS tide and water level operations consists of several different automated data processing (ADP) systems, assorted computers and software, and standard operating procedures, all of which require significant interaction by central office personnel, and are noted for their incompatibilities. The NGWLMS will reduce the numerous disparate systems to one integrated system.

The following are the ADP Tasks to be solved by the DPA Subsystem:

- o Provide for continuous automated data acquisition by dedicated telephone link between the National Environmental Satellite and Information Service (NESDIS) and the NGWLMS host computer;
- o Automate NWLON monitoring and control with automated data quality control;
- o Handle all data with a relational database management system (DBMS);
- o Minimize analyst interaction by automated data quality assurance procedures and data analyses;
- o Automate data and report management;

- o Improve the delivery time of verified data, derived products and services;

- o Provide remote users direct access and retrieval from the database with multi-level password control with automated tracking for management and billing; and

- o Provide expansion capability for high-speed automatic data dissemination.

To perform these tasks, the basic ADP resources--both hardware and software -- required for full implementation of the NGWLMS DPA Subsystem include:

- o a minicomputer with up to 19 megabytes of main memory capable of interactive, multi-tasking operations;

- o a relational DBMS that can handle up to 35 concurrent users with acceptable response time, and be capable of holding a minimum of 5,000 to 6,000 megabytes of information. (This DBMS is expected to reside on a dedicated machine -- either a special purpose database machine, or a general purpose minicomputer. Host interface software will be required);

- o terminals (mostly medium resolution graphics type, but some high resolution units, also);

- o printers (both laser and high speed line types);

- o plotters with color capability;

- o copiers with color capability connected to terminals.

Software, aside from the DBMS, would include an operating system(s), and associated system software. A commercial statistical package and a graphics package will also be included. Application software will include as much as is usable from the present systems, with the full suite of DPA software developed under a competitive contract.

The present computer system, based on a Concurrent Computer Corporation (CCC) Model 3210 with two megabytes of main memory is essentially an interactive system. Each oceanographer/analyst does much of the "thinking" required for data analysis.

The projected system will be structured around a relational DBMS, and will be much more automated than the present system. Recent estimates indicate the future system will need at least 16 megabytes of main memory to handle increased automation of DQA and analysis functions with the number of users expected for the DBMS.

Projected on-line storage beginning for FY 1987 workloads and continuing through the next six years are 2400 megabytes (MB) with off-line storage estimates at 6500 MB.

The NGWLMS system life is planned to be a minimum

TABLE II: PROTOTYPE NGWLMS FIELD UNIT LOCATIONS

STATION LOCATION	INSTALLATION DATE	SELECTION CRITERIA*
Shady Side, MD	01-14-86	Test (Temp., Aquatrak)
Shady Side, MD	01-14-86	Test (Temp., Aquatrak)
Duck Pier Outside, NC	01-15-86	C, L, VLBI, Test (Stat.)
Duck Pier Outside, NC	01-15-86	C, L, VLBI, Test (Stat.)
Duck Pier Outside, NC	01-15-86	C, L, VLBI, Test (Stat.)
Ches.Bay Br. Tunnel, VA	02-27-86	C, L, W, CM
Milwaukee, WI	03-25-86	W. Great Lakes
Lewes, DE	03-26-86	C, L, S, W, CM, P
Honolulu, OAHU, HI	04-03-86	C, L, T, H, P
San Francisco, CA	04-07-86	C, S, L, T, CM, H, P
Port Isabel, TX	04-10-86	C, S, H, Test (Temp. Var.)
Toke Point, WA	05-24-86	C, S, L, T
Rockville, MD	04-30-86	Test, Debug, Display
Corpus Christi, TX	05-01-86	C, L, S, H
Monterey, CA	05-20-86	C, L, H
Boston, MA	05-28-86	C, S, W, L, CM, H, P, VLBI
Anchorage, AK	07-18-86	C, S, P
Panama City, FL	07-31-86	C, MB, Test (Solar)
Lake Worth, FL	08-27-86	S, L, Test (EMI)
Haulover Beach Pier, FL	09-24-86	C, S, L, H, MB, VLBI

*KEY

C = Datum Control	MB = Marine Boundary	P = Tidal Prediction
S = Storm Surge Warning	T = Tsunami Warning	EMI = Electromagnetic Interference
W = Real Time Telemetry	CM = Circulation Modeling	VLBI = Very-Long Baseline Interferometry
L = Global Sea Level Monitoring	H = Hydrography/Nautical Charting	

TABLE III: HARDWARE DESCRIPTION OF PRODUCTION NGWLMS FIELD UNITS

GENERAL: The production field units will be an integrated measurement system consisting of a primary water level sensor, data collection platform (DCP), GOES transmitter and a backup pressure water level measurement system. The units will perform the same basic function as the prototype units with several system enhancements.

PRIMARY WATER LEVEL SENSOR

Air acoustic technique
 Range - 12 m
 Accuracy +/- 0.01 m
 Resolution - 0.003 m
 Correction temperature sensors -
 2 sensors, accuracy +/- 0.2 C

GOES SATELLITE TRANSMITTER

No significant changes

BACKUP WATER LEVEL SENSOR

Pressure sensor
 Range 0 to 15 m
 Accuracy +/- 0.015 m
 Resolution - 0.003 m
 Self-contained system
 Internal recording of most recent
 90 days

OPTIONAL ANCILLARY SENSOR PACKAGE

Wind Speed and Direction
 Barometric Pressure
 Air Temperature
 Water Temperature

DATA COLLECTION PLATFORM -Enhancements

Hardware:

Improved system packaging to simplify installation and maintenance. System memory 256K min. expandable to 512K - 30 days data storage. Ancillary sensor inputs expanded to 11 inputs, 4 RS-232 I/O ports, one 300/1200 baud telephone modem port and optional second external modem.

Firmware:

Expanded data collection capability to allow simultaneous averaging of ancillary sensors and primary water level data.
 User friendly I/O from either of the RS-232 ports or modems.
 Enhanced password scheme.
 Expanded data retrieval capabilities to allow collection for only selected sensors for selected time intervals.